

CORDEX Collection of Regional-Scale Climate Processes and Metrics for Climate Model Evaluation

2025-05-14

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15348836](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15348836)

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1. Introduction

This document reflects the results of ongoing WCRP-CORDEX activities to collect regional-scale climatic phenomena relevant for global climate model verification against observational datasets. The identified climate phenomena, a.k.a. “processes” or “diagnostics”, have distinct aspects (or features), each of which can be described by one or several “metrics”. The model error for a given diagnostic and aspect can then be calculated with an “error metric”, representing the final quantity we are interested in.

The present document complements the work of the *WCRP-CMIP Model Benchmarking Task Team (MB-TT)*, which currently focuses on global- or continental-scale diagnostics based on monthly input data. In contrast, the CORDEX approach operates at a finer scale, employing high-resolution diagnostics at the synoptic scale that require daily or sub-daily data. The results presented here are being shared with the MB-TT to foster synergies and support further decision-making.

2. Instructions on how to contribute to the table below

Please, provide examples in advance, gathering input from your regional communities and/or GCM verification studies. Process-oriented metrics are preferred, as basic biases will be computed anyway. The focus is on synoptic to meso-scale processes (a.k.a. “diagnostics”) that are ideally well resolved by GCMs (at least by the high resolution ones) and can be potentially improved by RCMs. Apart from metrics that evaluate the climatological aspects of the process itself, we would also like to assess how the impact on the regional climate is measured, following existing literature. To mention an example, the occurrence and intensity of atmospheric rivers, their link with (extreme) precipitation and role of “drought busters” ([Dettinger 2013](#)), meets all of these criteria in a number of CORDEX domains; see e.g. [Gröger et al. \(2022\)](#) for EUR. The final aim of the survey is to have a document everyone feels identified with, including regional experts the POCs may contact. Poorly defined examples are marked in red below and require further attention from the regional POCs.

3. Table of climate processes and metrics

Domain_id(s)	Process (a.k.a. diagnostic), regional impacts and metrics (one triple per row)	Publication(s)
EUR	<p>Process: Blocking frequency</p> <p>Regional impact: Drought, extreme heat spells in summer, extreme cold spells in winter</p> <p>Metric: 2D blocking index based on 3 indices describing meridional gradients in the 500hPa geopotential height field surrounding a specific grid-box (Davini et al. 2012, 2020)</p>	<p>Scherrer et al. (2006) Tibaldi & Molteni 2006 Davini et al. (2012) Davini and D'Andrea (2020)</p>
EUR, MED	<p>Process: North Atlantic Polar jet stream</p> <p>Regional impact: Determinant for storm tracks in EUR.</p> <p>Metric: latitudinal position bias. E.g. as estimated by the ONDJFM mean eddy-driven jet position over a given period, see Section 2 in Woolings et al. (2010) or Section 2.3.1 in Oudar et al. (2020a) for exact definitions; the metric is based on daily reanalysis wind data.</p>	<p>Woolings et al. (2010) Oudar et al. (2020a) Oudar et al. (2020b) Osso et al. (2024)</p>
EUR	<p>Process: Hess and Brezowsky Grosswetterlagen (HB-GWL)</p> <p>Regional impact: “The 29 Hess and Brezowsky Grosswetterlagen (HB-GWL) regimes can be viewed as readily identifiable large-scale circulation patterns involving the whole of Europe and the North-East Atlantic, with their primary focus on central Europe. The GWLs are also very meaningful in human terms, since their naming convention is intuitive and relates to the experience of weather spells in central Europe in particular.” James (2007). The scale is larger than that of the LWT approach</p> <p>Metric: Climatological Hess and Brezowsky Grosswetterlagen (HBG) frequencies</p>	<p>James (2007)</p>
EUR, MED, NAM, ARC, EAS, CAS, AFR, SAM, AUS, ANT (generally applicable between 30° and 70° latitude in both the Northern and Southern	<p>Process: Lamb Weather Types (LWTs)</p> <p>Regional impact: The climatological LWT frequency distribution describes expected variations in atmospheric flow and advected air-masses over a specific region. These, in turn, specify the regional climate conditions. Depending on the land-sea distribution and orography, specific weather types can trigger extreme precipitation events.</p> <p>Metric 1: Spatial-median mean absolute error in the</p>	<p>Brands (2022) Brands et al. (2023) Fernández Granja et al. (2023) Soares et al. (2023) Maraun et al. (2021)</p>

Hemisphere)	climatological Lamb Weather Type (LWT) frequencies over the respective CORDEX domain, as described in Brands (2022).	
EUR, MED, NAM, ARC, EAS, CAS, AFR, SAM, AUS, ANT Extratropics, mainly mid-latitudes	Process: fronts, their mesoscale dynamics, and the associated surface weather Regional impact: severe weather Metric: front frequency, mesoscale dynamics, dynamics - surface weather relationships	Schaffer et al. (2024) Schaffer et al. (in prep.)
EUR, MED, NAM, ARC, EAS, CAS, AFR, SAM, AUS, ANT Extratropics, mainly mid-latitudes	Process: cut-off low Regional impact: heavy rain Metric: cut-off low frequency, severity, duration, propagation speed	Mishra et al. (2025)
EUR, NAM, ARC, SAM, AUS, ANT, EA (mainly forming in the Sea of Japan)	Process: Polar Low (or Meso-scale Low) Regional impact: Heavy winds and waves, storm surge Metric: PL tracking algorithm of Zappa et al. (2014) based on instantaneous sub-daily vorticity maxima at 850 hPa	Zahn & von Storch (2008) , Zappa et al. (2014) , Yanase et al. (2016) , references for the Southern Hemisphere are needed
CAM	Process: Seasonal average of the Texas-Tam low-level jet (TLLJ, southern part of the GPLLJ): Regional impact: Jet is linked to spring/early summer rainfall and extreme events in the eastern US-Mexico border region. A strong TLLJ is associated with a strong CLLJ. Metric: V925 (meridional winds) over 24°N - 30°N and 100°W - 94°W (Colorado-Ruiz and Cavazos, 2025). Process: JJA and SON size of the Western Hemisphere warm pool (WHWP). Regional impact: The size of the WHWP is linked to El Niño (small size) and La Niña (large size) and thus to less (more) tropical cyclones. Metric: Area within SST equal or higher than 28.5°C in the CORDEX-CAM domain (Wang and Lee, 2008; Martinez-Sanchez and Cavazos, 2014) Process: Winter subtropical jet stream	Colorado-Ruiz, G, and T Cavazos. (2025) Li et al. (2011) Luna-Niño et al. (2021) Martinez-Sanchez & Cavazos (2014) Wang, C. & Lee (2007) Wang & Lee (2008)

	<p>Regional impact: Rainfall and temperature in the US - Mexico border region. The north/south position and intensity of the jet stream is linked to several teleconnections (ENSO, PNA, NAO, AO; Luna-Niño and Cavazos, 2021).</p> <p>Metric: Seasonal U200 (zonal winds). Distinct latitudinal indices for the west and east coast of the U.S. and Mexico:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Pacific jet: 15° N–45° N, 150° W–140° W 2. Coastal Pacific jet: 15° N–45° N, 90° W–65° W 3. Atlantic jet: 15° N–45° N, 132° W–115° W <p>1) Seasonal winds at 100 m height (I do not know if the CMIP models have this variable).</p> <p>2) Seasonal OLR</p>	
CAM	<p>Process: ENSO, disentangled by phase: During the warm (cold) phase of ENSO, precipitation in the Pacific (Caribbean) slope is lower (higher) than normal. The ENSO precipitation teleconnection is more consistent and stronger if the sign of the Caribbean/Atlantic ocean's SSTs anomalies are of opposite sign than the sign of the tropical Pacific SST anomaly, in a bipole fashion (e.g. Enfield and Alfaro, 1999, Maldonado et al., 2018, Durán-Quesada et al., 2020, Hidalgo et al., 2017).</p> <p>Regional impact: Impacts on society and environment can be found in Guevara-Murua et al. (2018), Méndez and Magaña (2010), Calvo-Solano et al. (2018); Peterson and Baringer (2009); Arndt et al, (2010); Blunden et al. (2011); Blunden and Arndt (2012; 2013;2014; 2015; 2016; 2017; 2019; 2020); Hartfield et al. 2018); Blunden and Boyer (2021; 2022; 2023; 2024); and others. In general, there are impacts on diverse natural and human systems such as the environment, ecology, agriculture, water resources, and others. It is also known that the number of tropical cyclones in the Caribbean basin increases (decreases) during El Niño (La Niña) events (Gray; 1984).</p> <p>Metrics: ENSO indices, ENSO precipitation teleconnection for Central America is not very well reproduced in CMIP5 models, probably because even precipitation norms are not reproduced well (Hidalgo and Alfaro, 2015). Due to the complex terrain and narrowness of the isthmus, high resolution estimates from downscaled data may help improve this. The skill of the ENSO-precipitation teleconnection in CMIP6 models can be found in Gómez et al. (2024).</p> <p>Metric: The following method is used for ENSO-PR</p>	<p>Enfield & Alfaro (1999) Durán-Quesada et al. (2020) Maldonado et al. (2018) Hidalgo et al. (2017) Calvo-Solano et al. (2018) Hartfield et al. (2018) Blunden & Boyer (2024) Hidalgo & Alfaro (2015) Gómez et al. (2024) Gray (1984) Guevara-Morúa et al. (2018) Méndez & Magaña (2010)</p>

	<p>teleconnection (Hidalgo and Alfaro 2015):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Niño1.2 time series (see location of the averaging area in Figure 1) was calculated from the observed NOAA/OAR/ESRL PSD SST data for DJF for each year from 1979 to 1999. • The precipitation time series was calculated from the observed GPCP data for each grid point in the target area (4°–20°N, 95°–75°W) for DJF for each year from 1979 to 1999. • Temporal correlation coefficients between the Niño1.2 time series and the precipitation time series for all the grid points in the target area were calculated. This gave a two-dimensional distribution of correlation coefficients over the target area (i.e. the teleconnection pattern). • The process was repeated for DJF Niño1.2 and DJF precipitation time series derived for each CMIP5 model runs. • The process was repeated for the Niño3, Niño3.4 and Niño4 regions during DJF. • The process was repeated for MAM, JJA, SON and annual averages of the ENSO indexes and precipitation data. 	
CAM	<p>Process: Teleconnections with the Tropical North Atlantic (TNA) index</p> <p>Regional impact: ?</p> <p>Metric: As for ENSO, but using the TNA index instead</p> <p>Info: For TNA, there is no study available of the skill of GCMs on reproducing that specific index.</p>	
CAM	<p>Process: Caribbean Low-level Jet (CLLJ). The CLLJ is an area in the Caribbean where the trade winds at the 925hPa level are particularly strong (approx. 10 m s⁻¹). It is a very consistent feature during the year (Amador 1998; 2008), but it has maximums in February and July. It is not entirely independent of ENSO, as during the warm (cold) phase of ENSO, the CLLJ is usually stronger (weaker) (Hidalgo et al. 2015, 2019; Colorado-Ruiz and Cavazos, 2025). Strong CLLJ is associated with lower (higher) than normal precipitation in the Pacific Caribbean slope of Central America (Hidalgo et al., 2019). A physical mechanism on how this teleconnection occurs can be found in Hidalgo et al. (2015).</p> <p>Regional Impact: The CLLJ is known to be related to dryness in</p>	<p>Amador (1998) Amador (2008) Hidalgo et al. (2015) Hidalgo et al. (2015) Ley et al. (2024) Gotlieb et al. (2019) Colorado-Ruiz & Cavazos (2025) and</p>

	<p>the Pacific slope, especially in the higher aridity region in Central America, known as the Central America Dry Corridor (CADC; Hidalgo et al., 2019; Ley et al. 2024). The CADC is known to be a socio-economic vulnerable subregion to drought, with communities that rely heavily on subsistence agriculture (Hidalgo et al. 2019; Gotlieb et al. 2019). The CLLJ is associated with the TLLJ in the eastern US-Mexico border region and different rainfall impacts in Eastern and Southern Mexico (Colorado-Ruiz and Cavazos, 2025), particularly mid-summer drought.</p> <p>Metric: Caribbean Low-level Jet Index (Amador et al., 1998; 2008; Hidalgo et al., 2015) . The index is defined as the monthly zonal wind at the 925 hPa pressure level averaged over the region 75–12.5°N and 85–75°W. A comparison of the monthly climatology of the CLLJ index of several CMIP5 models and NCEP/NCAR reanalysis can be found in Hidalgo and Alfaro (2015).</p>	
CAM	<p>Process: Tropical Cyclones; Tropical cyclones are one feature that produces significant impacts in Central America (Quesada-Román et al., 2024; Hidalgo et al. 2020; 2022), and Mexico (Colorado-Ruiz and Cavazos, 2025). Direct impacts in northern Central America and indirect impacts in southern Central America are usually associated with active tropical cyclone seasons. Weaker (very active) tropical cyclone seasons are usually associated with the warm (cold) phase of ENSO (REF). Indirect effects from Caribbean tropical cyclones are usually registered as extremely wet precipitation in the Pacific slope of southern Central America (Peña and Douglas, 2002; Hidalgo et al., 2020).</p> <p>Regional Impact: flooding and landslides are usually associated with direct and indirect impacts of tropical cyclones (Pérez-Briceño et al., 2020; Alfaro and Quesada, 2010; Alfaro and Pérez-Briceño, 2014; Qesada-Román et al., 2024; Hidalgo et al., 2020; 2022; Peña and Douglas, 2002; Maldonado et al., 2020)</p> <p>Metrics: HURDAT trajectory data. Cyclone characteristics in the Central America domain using RegCM4 model can be found in Diro et al. (2014).</p>	<p>Pérez-Briceño et al. (2016) Alfaro and Quesada (2010) Alfaro & Pérez-Briceño (2014) Quesada-Román et al. (2024) Hidalgo et al. (2020) Hidalgo et al. (2022) Peña and Douglas (2002) Maldonado et al. (2020) Diro et al. (2014) Colorado-Ruiz & Cavazos (2025)</p>
CAM	<p>Process: The North-Atlantic Subtropical High (NASH) is considered one of the main drivers of climate variability in Central America and eastern Mexico, modulating the strength of the trade-winds (Gill 1980; Taylor and Alfaro 2005; Wang 2007; Colorado-Ruiz and Cavazos, 2025). Higher (weaker) pressure anomalies in the NASH increases (decreases) the</p>	<p>Gill (1980) Taylor and Alfaro (2005) Wang (2007) Hidalgo et al. (2017) Hidalgo et al. (2019) Li et al. (2015)</p>

	<p>strength of the trade winds in the Caribbean producing dryness (wetness) in the Pacific slope.</p> <p>Regional Impact: Higher NASH and trade winds are associated with drier conditions in the Pacific slope of Central America (Hidalgo et al., 2017; 2019). The impact in eastern Mexico depends on the intensity and western extension of the NASH (Colorado-Ruiz and Cavazos, 2025); a western extended and intense NASH is linked to drier conditions.</p> <p>Metric: Seasonal average of the western ridge of the NASH: Z850 over 20°N - 40°N and 80°W - 25°W (Li et al., 2011; Colorado-Ruiz and Cavazos, 2025).</p> <p>Info: In a study to determine the skill of RCMs in simulating southeastern United States Summer precipitation the physical mechanisms responsible for the simulation skill at a process level were explored, including the NASH (Li et al., 2015). Studies using AGCMs to study NASH are found in Wei et al. (2018) and Chen et al. (2022). For Central America's climate teleconnections, the reader can refer to Martinez et al. (2019) and Cavazos et al. (2019).</p>	<p>Wei et al. (2018) Chen et al. (2022) Martinez et al. (2019) Cavazos et al. (2019)</p>
CAM	<p>Process: Intertropical convergence zone (ITCZ). Region of confluence of trade winds from the northern and southern hemisphere, which causes high-precipitation when it is located over Central America. It has strong seasonality in position and strength (Hidalgo et al., 2015; Quirós and Hidalgo 2016a; 2016b). The position of the ITCZ and the intensity of the westerly winds off the southern coasts of Mexico modulate extreme rainfall and seasonal rainfall in southern and eastern Mexico (Colorado-Ruiz and Cavazos (2025) and references within).</p> <p>Regional impact: During the wet season, the locations influenced by the ITCZ will experience flooding and heavy rainfall.</p> <p>Metrics: Position and strength indices of the ITCZ can be found in Quirós and Hidalgo (2016a; 2016b). Some characteristics of the ITCZ shape in CMIP5 models and reanalysis can be found in Hidalgo and Alfaro (2015).</p>	<p>Hidalgo et al. (2015) Quirós and Hidalgo (2016a) Quirós and Hidalgo (2016b) Hidalgo and Alfaro (2015) Colorado-Ruiz & Cavazos (2025)</p>
CAM	<p>Process: Mid-Summer Drought (MSD). Local reduction of precipitation in the Pacific slope meteorological stations during the months of July or August (Magaña et al. 1999). A summary of the mechanisms responsible for the MSD can be found in García-Franco et al. (2023). Other studies on the MSD can be found in Maurer et al. (2022); Maldonado et al. (2016)</p>	<p>Maurer et al. (2022) Maldonado et al. (2016) Magaña et al. (1999) Perdigón-Morales et al.</p>

	<p>and Perdigón-Morales et al. (2018).</p> <p>Regional impact:. The magnitude and duration of the MSD affects agriculture and crop yield (Jobbová et al. 2018; Harvey et al. 2018)</p> <p>Metrics: Indices of describing its frequency, duration, magnitude and intensity of MSD can be computed (UNESCO, 2021). For comparison between GCMs and reanalysis of MSD indices, we refer to Maurer et al. (2017).</p>	<p>(2018)</p> <p>García-Franco et al. (2023)</p> <p>Jobbová et al. (2018)</p> <p>Harvey et al. (2018)</p> <p>Maurer et al. (2017)</p>
CAM	<p>Other processes: Complex topography, distance to the sea, boreal winter cold-fronts or outbreaks, “temporales”, sea breeze circulations, the Pacific Decadal Oscillation (PDO), the Atlantic Multidecadal Oscillation (AMO); cold-fronts; Western Hemisphere Warm Pool (WHWP); moisture transport; Madden Julian Oscillation (MJO) and easterly-waves (Ley et al., 2023; Alfaro and Pérez-Briceño, 2014; Durán-Quesada et al., 2020).</p> <p>Regional impacts: large-scale, synoptic, mesoscale and local scale climate precursors combine in linear and non-linear ways to produce impacts in human and environmental systems (Ley et al., 2023; Durán-Quesada et al., 2020).</p> <p>Metrics: ocean and atmosphere indices. While some of these processes have been studied extensively (see references in Ley et al., 2023; Durán-Quesada et al., 2020), others require more basic research; but these are some of the topics more needed to be advanced in the modeling and understanding of their teleconnections with the Central American climate.</p>	<p>Ley et al (2023)</p> <p>Martinez et al. (2014)</p> <p>Durán-Quesada et al. (2020)</p> <p>Luna-Niño and Cavazos, 2018</p>
MED	<p>Process: Future changes in 3 key remote drivers: tropical amplification, polar warming and stratospheric polar vortex strength and associated GCM families (storyline approach, Zappa and Shepherd 2017, Mindlin et al. 2021)</p> <p>Regional Impact: the storylines strongly influence the change in winter precipitation and cyclone activity for the Mediterranean area (see Zappa and Shepherd 2017; Reale et al., 2021). For example, GCMs with strong tropical amplification and polar vortex strengthening show a strong winter drying in the Mediterranean area.</p> <p>Metric: same computation as in Zappa and Shepherd 2017. The metrics have been computed by Julia Mindling for 36 CMIP6 GCMs whereas the initial study deals with CMIP5. Results can be found on github: https://github.com/jumin94/remote_driver_indices/tree/main</p>	<p>Zappa & Shepherd (2017)</p> <p>Mindlin et al. (2021)</p> <p>Reale et al. (2021)</p>

MED	<p>Process: GCM past behaviour for the ocean surface layer (0–150 m) temperature and salinity characteristics of the North-Atlantic zone close to the Gibraltar Strait.</p> <p>Regional Impact: This surface layer enters the Mediterranean Sea through the Strait of Gibraltar and strongly influences its water mass characteristics. GCM with biases water masses in the surface Atlantic Ocean should be avoided to drive Med-CORDEX coupled RCMs</p> <p>Metric: long-term mean GCM bias for temperature and salinity values integrated over the 0–150m layer in the Near-Atlantic Ocean box (contact: Javier Soto-Navarro)</p>	Soto-Navarro and Jordà, in prep.
MED	<p>Others: (See the GCM selection Task Team work, https://zenodo.org/records/11655156 And the associated github page https://wcrp-cordex.github.io/cmip6-for-cordex/CMIP6_studies_table_MED.html)</p>	https://zenodo.org/records/11655156
SAM	<p>Process: Climatological individual and compound extremes in CORDEX-CORE RCMs and GCMs for SAM</p> <p>Regional Impact: Added value of RCM</p> <p>Metric: Maps of Ensemble BIAS vs ERA5 (Olmo et al. 2022a)</p>	Olmo et al. (2022a)
SAM	<p>Process: Circulation patterns-CPs (u850,v850), their spatial structure and associated rainfall.</p> <p>Regional impact: SAM Monsoon onset and demise</p> <p>Metric: seasonal frequency distribution of CPs during dry-to-wet transition season (July-October). Error metric: absolute difference between the observed and GCM CPs climatological daily frequencies. Taylor diagrams for CPs spatial structure. Rank-based Kendall tau coefficient for mean seasonal PP and dry-day frequency (Olmo et al. 2022b).</p>	Olmo et al. (2022b)
SAM	<p>Process: GCMs ability in reproducing the observed atmospheric circulation patterns (Z500, CPs) in Southern South America</p> <p>Regional Impact: associated precipitation over Southern South America and uncertainty in projections.</p> <p>Metric: GCM CPs vs ERA5 CPs: Bias in frequency and Self Organizing Map node frequency correlation. Conditional precipitation to CPs, Taylor Diagrams (Olmo et al. 2023).</p>	Olmo et al. (2023)

SAM	<p>Process: Climatological precipitation and mean temperature in Colombia</p> <p>Regional impact: Selection of the models with the best simulations for mean precipitation and temperature in Colombia, comparison with CORDEX simulations</p> <p>Metric: Climatological annual cycles, Taylor diagrams of the seasonal patterns</p>	Arias et al. (2021)
SAM	<p>Process: Climatological precipitation and mean temperature in Central America and South America</p> <p>Regional impact: Selection of the models with the best simulations for mean seasonal/annual precipitation and temperature in six biodiverse regions of Central America and South America (Central America, Guianas, Andes hotspot, central Chile, Chaco region, Cerrado)</p> <p>Metric: climatological annual cycles for each region, Taylor diagrams of the seasonal patterns for the entire Central and South America domain and for each of the six regions (Ortega et al. 2021).</p>	Ortega et al. (2021)
SAM	<p>Process: Choco low-level jet (Choco LLJ)</p> <p>Regional impact: Influence of land-sea thermal contrast on regional atmospheric circulation, evaluation of Choco LLJ jets in PMIP and CMIP simulations, changes of the Choco LLJ during past (Last Millenium), present (recent decades) and future (late 21st century) periods</p> <p>Metric: monthly Choco LLJ index, jet latitudinal location, jet intensity, vertical structure of zonal winds, 925hPa horizontal wind fields, eastern Pacific/landmass thermal contrasts, regional sea level pressure gradients (Sierra et al. 2021)</p>	Sierra et al. 2021
SAM	<p>Process: Atmospheric moisture transport in northern South America</p> <p>Regional impact: Evaluation of models in the representation of atmospheric moisture transport from different sources, mean evaporation, precipitable water</p> <p>Metric: Taylor diagrams for mean seasonal precipitation (P), evaporation (E), precipitable water (PW) and P-E, mean total annual and mean annual cycles of the precipitable water/precipitation contributions from different moisture sources to northern South America (NWS and NES IPCC AR6</p>	Arias et al. (2023)

	regions), and the Amazon (SAM IPCC AR6 region) (Arias et al. 2023)	
SAM	<p>Process: Orinoco low-level jet (OLLJ)</p> <p>Regional impact: Atmospheric moisture transport and land-surface processes in the Orinoco region (NSA region of the IPCC AR6), selection of the models with the best OLLJ simulations</p> <p>Metric: monthly OLLJ index, seasonal vertical structure of the wind field, and seasonal spatial distribution of the 925–850 hPa horizontal wind (Correa et al. 2024)</p>	Correa et al. (2024)
SAM	<p>Process: Boundary conditions for regional simulations of South America</p> <p>Regional impact: Systematic evaluation of more than 50 GCMs in their representation of different aspects of South American climate, including moisture and heat fluxes across South American boundaries</p> <p>Metrics: Atlantic trade winds, South American westerlies, subtropical highs (South Pacific, North Atlantic, South Atlantic), Bolivian High, Polar jet, Subtropical jet, vertically integrated moisture fluxes, vertically integrated heat fluxes, ENSO, Taylor Diagrams of different seasonal patterns (850hPa winds, 200hPa winds, SSTs, SLPs, precipitation, Hadley cell, Walker cell) (Arias et al. 2025, under review)</p>	Arias et al. 2025, under review
SAM	<p>Process: South American Monsoon onset and demise</p> <p>Regional Impact: Precipitation season in tropical and subtropical SAM</p> <p>Metrics:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Monsoon onset and ending dates based on pentad (5-day averaged) outgoing longwave radiation (OLR) for a fixed threshold of 240Wm², considering the preceding and subsequent pentads. Kousky V. E. (1988). Pentad outgoing longwave radiation climatology for the South America sector. Revista Brasileira de Meteorologia 3, 217–231. 2) The onset and ending date based on pentad (5-day averaged) precipitation exceeding 4 mm day⁻¹, considering the preceding and subsequent pentads. Marengo et al (2001). Onset and end of the rainy season in the Brazilian Amazon basin. J. Climate 14, 833–852 	

	<p><a href="https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0442(2001)014<0833:OAEOTR>2.0.CO;2">https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0442(2001)014<0833:OAEOTR>2.0.CO;2</p> <p>3) The onset date is defined using the accumulation of precipitation in days when daily precipitation is larger than the climatology for that day. Liebmann and Marengo, (2001). <a href="https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0442(2001)014<4308:IVOTRS>2.0.CO;2">https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0442(2001)014<4308:IVOTRS>2.0.CO;2</p> <p>4) Indices based on circulation: the authors argued that these indices are better suited for GCM evaluation than precipitation indices.</p> <p>*MWSI: Meridional wind shear index</p> <p>*ZWSI: Zonal wind shear index</p> <p>*850 hPa zonal wind index</p> <p>*UVI: averaged 850 hPa zonal wind and meridional wind over a threshold of 12 m/s</p> <p>Gan MA, et al (2007) South American monsoon indices. Atmospheric Science Letters https://doi.org/10.1002/asl.119</p>	
SAM	<p>Process: Atmospheric Rivers</p> <p>Regional Impact: Extreme Precipitation</p> <p>Metric: AR detection algorithm applied to a 6-hourly gridded integrated water vapor transport (IVT) field and AR landfall - at least one of the AR axis grid cells overlaps with the land mask of the reanalysis Viale et al. (2018)</p>	Viale et al. (2018)
SAM	<p>Process: South Atlantic Convergence Zone (SACZ) position and variability</p> <p>Regional Impact: Precipitation variability during the warm season in Southeastern South America</p> <p>Metric: First EOF of OLR in Southeastern South America. (Barros et al. 2000, Vera et al 2018)</p>	<p>Barros et al. 2000</p> <p>Vera et al 2018</p>
SAM	<p>Process: South America Low Level Jet (SALLJ)</p> <p>Regional Impact: Intense water vapor transport towards extratropical latitudes. Extreme precipitation events over La</p>	<p>Bonner 1968</p> <p>Marengo et al. (2004)</p> <p>Montini et al. (2019)</p>

	<p>Plata Basin.</p> <p>Metric: Identification criteria:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Bonner 1: 850 hPa maximum wind intensity equal to or greater than 12 m/s; Wind shear 850–700 hPa equal to or greater than 6 m/s in some region enclosed by the 12 m/s isotach at 850 hPa; 850 hPa northern meridional wind greater than the zonal wind throughout the region enclosed by the 12 m/s isotach. (Bonner 1968) 2) Similar to Bonner 1 but less restrictive regarding the region enclosed by the 12m/s isotach (Marengo et al. 2004) 3) Similar to Bonner 1, except for the threshold. It uses the 75th percentile instead of 12 m/s (Montini et al. 2019) 	<p>Ashfaq et al. (2020)</p>
<p>SAM</p>	<p>Other suggested but poorly defined diagnostics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ENSO indices • Location of upper level jets • Location of semi permanent anticyclones (South Atlantic and South Pacific) • ITCZ position (Liu et al. 2020) • Exploratory Precipitation metrics (Leung et al. 2022) 	<p>Relevant articles:</p> <p>Rusticucci et al. (2016)</p> <p>Marianetti et al (2024)</p> <p>Collazo et al (2023)</p> <p>Gateño et al (2024)</p> <p>Navarro-Raciles et al. (2020)</p> <p>Villegas & Chaliner (2012)</p> <p>Zhang et al. (2024)</p>
<p>AUS</p>	<p>Process: ENSO</p> <p>Regional impact: ?</p> <p>Metric: Calculated using the Niño-3.4 index</p> <p>Process: Indian Ocean Dipole (IOD)</p> <p>Regional impact:</p> <p>Metric: Calculated using Dipole Mode Index, defined as the difference of SST anomalies in the west equatorial Indian Ocean (50 to 70°E, 10°S to 10°N) minus those in the east (90</p>	<p>Di Virgo et al. (2022)</p> <p>Grose et al (2023)</p> <p>Chapman et al (2023)</p> <p>Gibson et al (2024)</p>

	<p>to 110°E, 10°S to 0°).</p> <p>Process: Southern Annular Mode</p> <p>Regional Impact: ?</p> <p>Metric: SAM index calculated as the difference in zonal mean sea level pressure anomalies between 40°S and 65°S.</p> <p>Other suggested but poorly defined diagnostics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Subtropical ridge (STR) ● Subtropical jet position and strength (JET) ● Process Storm tracks ● Process: Drought indices 	
ANT	<p>Process: Storyline approach (Shepherd et al. 2018) Based on input from the polar impact modelling community, storylines were developed for the Antarctic based on future sea ice loss and stratospheric polar strength (Williams et al., 2024).</p> <p>Regional impact:</p> <p>Metrics: Storyline approach described in Shepherd et al. (2018). The remote climate drivers of the Antarctic climate are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Change in sea ice extent (both Williams et al. 2024) ● Hemispheric sum of the area of the grid cells for which the sea ice concentration is at least 15% (the standard threshold between ice and open water) ● Stratospheric polar vortex strength (both Williams et al. 2024): Seasonal-mean U50 area-averaged for the latitude range 50°–60°S, consistent with that used in Mindlin et al. (2020) July to August (austral winter) and November+December (austral summer). The SSP585 scenario was used to calculate future increments. 	<p>Shepherd et al. (2018)</p> <p>Mindlin et al. (2020)</p> <p>Williams et al. (2024)</p>
ARC	<p>Process: storyline approach (Shepherd et al. 2018). The remote climate drivers of the Arctic climate are:</p> <p>Regional impact: ?</p> <p>Metrics (Levine et al., 2024):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Warming of the average sea-surface temperature in the Barents–Kara seas ● Arctic Amplification represented by change in 	<p>Levine et al. (2024)</p>

	<p>850 hPa temperature averaged over all areas poleward of 55° N.</p> <p>The SSP585 scenario was used to calculate the delta change estimates.</p>	
NAM	<p>Process: Climate model Weighting by Independence and Performance (ClimWIP) approach (Brunner et al. 2020, Merrifield et al. 2023), adopted to Canada as described in Matte et al. (2025)</p> <p>Regional impact: ?</p> <p>Metric: for annual maximum snow amount, GCM are selected according to tas-clim, pr-clim and snwmax-clim over Canadian territory, as well as psl Synop. Act. over a larger domain including the U.S., the North Pacific and North Atlantic (30–70°N, 50–140°W). See Matte et al. (2025) for details.</p> <p>Process: Model selection dashboard over NAM and NAM IPCC regions : hus, tas, pr, sicconcMaxext and sicconcMinext, zg500 and zg500var, https://pavics.ouranos.ca/selection-de-modeles</p> <p>Regional impact: ?</p> <p>Metric: ?</p> <p>Other poorly defined processes:</p> <p>HU-850 hPa, TAS, Mean 500 hPa GZ, 2–6 days band passed filtered 500 hPa GZ variance, Sea ice (maximum and minimum extent), SST.</p>	Matte et al (2025)
NAM	<p>Process: Atmospheric rivers</p> <p>Regional impact: Heavy precipitation</p> <p>Metric:</p>	<p>Vallejo-Bernal et al. (2023)</p> <p>Zhou, Y., J. North, A.M. Rhoades, J. Tao, W. Rudisill, M. Risser, and W.D. Collins (2025) “Atmospheric river frequency-category characteristics shaping U.S. west coast runoff” Submitted to <i>J. Geophys. Res. Atmos.</i></p>
NAM	<p>Process: North American monsoon</p>	Hoell et al. 2013

	<p>Regional impact: precipitation / drought</p> <p>Metric:</p>	
NAM	<p>Process: Winter extratropical cyclones</p> <p>Regional impact: Winter : Nor'easter, blizzards, rain on snow, storm surge, coastal erosion</p> <p>Metric : density, propagation speed, precipitation, landing</p>	Basu & Sauchin (2023)
NAM	<p>Process : Tropical cyclones and hurricanes</p> <p>Regional impact: extreme precipitation and winds, flooding</p> <p>Metric : density, propagation speed, precipitation, landing</p>	
MENA	<p>Process: Dust Cycle Representation and Atmospheric Feedbacks</p> <p>Regional impacts: Mineral dust, a major component of aerosols, profoundly affects the Earth's climate system , air quality , human health and the fertilization of iron-deficient marine ecosystems “ (Kunchala et al. 2024).</p> <p>Metrics: Temporal (based on monthly-mean time-series) Correlation Coefficients of Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) at 550 nm averaged over the over MENA (20°W and 65° E and 15°N and 35°N which encompasses the major dust loading regions of Saharan Desert and Arabian Peninsula).</p> <hr/> <p>Process: Hadley Circulation (HC) strength (Pikovnik et al. 2022)</p> <p>Regional impact: warming amplifier; exacerbation of aridity in already water-stressed regions</p> <p>Metrics:</p> <p>1) Maximum of annual/seasonal-mean stream function (ψ_{max}) between 40°S and 40°N, and between 200 and 900 hPa,</p> <p>2) Maximum of the zonal-mean vertical (pressure) velocity $\omega_{max}(p)$, i.e. maximum descent, at 500 hPa between 20°W and 65° E and 15°N and 40°N.</p>	<p>Kunchala et al. (2024)</p> <hr/> <p>Pikovnik M, Zaplotnik Ž, Boljka L, Žagar N (2022)</p> <hr/>

	<p>Process: Poleward migration of Subtropical High (STH)</p> <p>Regional impact: Same as for Hadley Circulation</p> <p>Metric: STH position (Francis & Fonseca 2024): maximum of the 500 hPa geopotential height over North Africa (0°–35° N; 15° W–30° E) and Arabian Peninsula (5°–35° N; 35°–60° E)</p>	Francis D, Fonseca R (2024)
MENA	<p>Process: North–Atlantic circulation (weather regimes)</p> <p>Regional impact: Large effect on precipitation in Northwest Africa (Balhane et al. 2022)</p> <p>Metric: ?, can perhaps be found in El Ouaraini et al. (2025)</p>	El Ouaraini et al. (2025) Balhane et al. (2022)
MENA	<p>Process: Saharan Heat Low</p> <p>Regional impact: The Saharan Heat low impacts (summer) temperatures and can exacerbate hot extreme events. Furthermore, Interactions with west African Monsoon. Enhanced Saharan heat low results in enhanced moist advection in west africa, involving dust</p> <p>Metrics: location, mean intensity, global trend, interaction with the West African monsoon dynamics (Lavaysse et al. 2016, Dixon et al. 2017)</p>	Dixon et al (2017) Lavaysse et al. (2016) Pan et al. (2018) is seemingly related to the relationship between Saharan dust and tropical cyclones. Please provide the corresponding doi!
MENA	<p>Process: Tropical plumes</p> <p>Regional impact: extreme precipitation events</p> <p>Metric: ?</p>	Tubi et al. (2017) Hamich et al. (2025) Sahlaoui et al. (2022)
MENA	<p>Process: Tropical-extratropical interactions</p> <p>Regional impact: precipitation</p> <p>Metric: ?</p>	Knippertz et al. (2003), Knippertz(2007)
MENA	<p>Other poorly defined processes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Same aspect as MED • Plus SHL 	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tropical-extratropical interactions 	
AFR	<p>Process: West African Monsoon</p> <p>Regional impact: Precipitation</p> <p>Metrics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Onset and withdrawal - Hovmoller diagram over monsoon domain - Timing of the Upper troposphere temperature gradient (MTG) reversal - Teleconnections 	<p>Ashfaq et al, 2020 (Onset and withdrawal, Hovmoller, MTG reversal)</p> <p>Horan et al. 2024</p>
AFR	<p>Process: East African monsoons</p> <p>Regional impact: Precipitation driver</p> <p>Metrics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Onset and withdrawal - Hovmoller diagram over monsoon domain - Timing of the Upper troposphere temperature gradient (MTG) reversal 	
AFR	<p>Process: Southeast Africa monsoon</p> <p>Regional impact: Precipitation driver</p> <p>Metrics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Onset and withdrawal - Hovmoller diagram over monsoon domain - Timing of the Upper troposphere temperature gradient (MTG) reversal - Teleconnections with ENSO, IOD 	
AFR	<p>Process: African Easterly Jets (AEJ)</p> <p>Regional impact: Important for the central African rain (Creese & Washington 2017, Kuete et al. 2020,2023)</p> <p>Metric: low to mid-tropospheric easterly wind. The location and intensity are determined by easterly wind speed > 6m/s between 10E and 30E (Kuete et al. 2023):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For the northern branch of AEJ (AEJ-N), 700hPa easterly wind between 0–20N is used - For the southern branch (AEJ-S), it's the 600hPa 	<p>Creese and Washington (2017)</p> <p>Kuete et al. (2020)</p> <p>Kuete et al. (2023)</p>

	easterly wind between 20S-0	
AFR	<p>Process: Angola low-pressure system (Angola Low)</p> <p>Regional impact: a dominant mechanism driving the southern African rainfall</p> <p>Metric: lowest 5% of DJF mean 850 hPa geopotential height values within a large southern African domain (5–55°E, 0–35°S, Munday & Washington 2017)</p>	Munday and Washington (2017)
AFR	<p>Process: Mozambique Channel Trough (MCT)</p> <p>Regional impact: mechanism leading to the rainfall dipole pattern over the southern African subcontinent</p> <p>Metric: The MCT index is defined as the area average of the relative vorticity at 850 hPa over the southern Mozambique Channel (35–44°E, 16–26°S), derived from monthly data Barimalala et al. (2024).</p>	Barimalala et al. (2024)
AFR	<p>Process: Mascarene High</p> <p>Regional Impact: Drives the Findlater jet at its northern flank and thus precipitation along the East African coast.</p> <p>Metric: The MH index is defined as the area averaged of the mean sea level pressure (MSLP) within 40–110°E and 15–40°S (Barimalala et al. 2024, Section 2 and Figure 2)</p>	Barimalala et al. (2024)
AFR	<p>Process: Findlater Jet (FJ) aka East African Low Level Jet</p> <p>Regional Impact: Precipitation driver through moisture advection along the coast of East Africa. “The East African LLJ accounts for about half the cross-equatorial transport of water vapor in the western Indian Ocean (from 75° East to the African coast)” (Barry & Carleton 2001, ISBN 0–415–03116–8)</p> <p>Metric: Mean positional error of the July-mean maximum wind speed at 925 hPa over the western Indian Ocean and East Africa (Figure 1 in Findlater 1971, has to be exactly defined). Consider better definitions based on integrated water vapour flux (IVT)</p>	Findlater (1971), Findlater (1977), Hart (1977)
AFR	<p>Process: Tropical Temperate Trough (or Tropical-extratropical cloud bands)</p>	Hart et al. (2012) Hart et al. (2018)

	<p>Regional impact: Precipitation driver</p> <p>Metric: Daily mean outgoing longwave radiation over southern Africa (Hart et al. 2012, 2018)</p>	See also Hart's previous work on cloud bands
AFR	<p>Process: Nocturnal easterly Low-Level Jets (LLJs)</p> <p>Regional Impact: Precipitation driver in central Africa through moisture advection from the Indian Ocean through the valleys of the East African rift system</p> <p>Metric: ?</p>	Munday et al. (2020)
AFR	<p>Other poorly defined processes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ENSO (OND rain for eastern Africa, JJAS for West African Monsoon, DJFM rain for southern Africa) - IOD (OND and JJAS rain for eastern Africa, SON for central Africa, DJFM for part of southern Africa) - SAM and SIOD (DJFM rain for southern Africa) - Tropical Atlantic (JJAS for the west African monsoon, and JJAS in eastern Africa) 	
AFR, SAM, NAM, MENA, CAM, WAS, EAS, SEA, AUS	<p>Climatological frequency of Tropical Easterly Waves (TEW), called African Easterly Waves in Africa (see above)</p> <p>Regional impact: "TEWs are known to impact precipitation, affecting summertime rainfall patterns in many regions (Moron et al. 2008; Dominguez et al. 2020), modulating pre-monsoonal rainfall in the northern Indian basin (Sawaisarje et al. 2019), and priming the atmosphere for extreme rainfall events (Engel et al. 2017)" (Hollis et al. 2024)</p> <p>Metric: Climatological occurrence frequency (Hollis et al. 2024)</p>	Hollis et al. (2024)
WAS, EA, SEA, AUS, AFR	<p>Process: Madden-Julian Oscillation (MJO)</p> <p>Regional Impact: The MJO strongly modulates rainfall in the tropics and subtropics, affecting monsoon onset, active/break phases, and tropical cyclone activity. It also influences mid-latitude weather patterns through interactions with the jet stream and atmospheric circulation.</p> <p>Metric: Modelled vs. observed Hovmöller diagram of longitude-binned spatial average Outgoing Longwave Radiation (OLR) in the inner tropics (10°S to 10°N or</p>	<p>Zhang (2005) Hovmöller 1949 Back et al. (2024) Lin et al. (2024)</p>

	15°S to 15°N) via, e.g. the Taylor diagram, to evaluate the representation and propagation of the MJO signal. Alternative metrics are described in Lin et al. (2024) and Back et al. (2024)	
WAS	<p>Process: Summer monsoon</p> <p>Regional impact: Precipitation driver; “The ISM accounts for 70% of annual precipitation over India and 60% of agriculture sector jobs” (Kushwaha et al. 2022)</p> <p>Metrics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Onset and withdrawal - timing of the reversal of meridional tropospheric temperature (MTG) gradient - Vertical easterly shear (between V200 and V850) - Vertical Meridional Shear (between U200 and U850), strength and timing of reversal - Monsoon lows and depression (frequency and tracks) - Teleconnection with ENSO - Apparent heat source (Q1) - Moisture sources 	<p>Ashfaq et al. (2017) Ashfaq et al. (2020) Feng et al. (2013) Mei et al. (2015) Rastogi et al. 2018 Kushwaha et al. 2022</p>
WAS	<p>Process: Subtropical westerly jet (SWJ)</p> <p>Regional Impact: Cold season precipitation</p> <p>Metrics: Position and strength</p>	<p>Hunt et al. (2025)</p>
WAS	<p>Process: Western disturbances (embedded in the SWJ)</p> <p>Regional Impact: Cold season precipitation</p> <p>Metric: frequency and tracks; Moet calculated the tracks and frequency of these disturbances using the method outlined by Kevin Hodges (University of Reading) in Kapnick et al. (2014), as presented in the supplementary figures. This data can be used to determine the mean track of these western disturbances. We demonstrated that in a similar example in the case of monsoon depressions in Rastogi et al. (2018), Figure 1.</p>	<p>Hunt et al. (2025) Feng et al. (2013) Kapnick et al. (2014) Rastogi et al. (2018)</p>
WAS	<p>Process: ENSO Teleconnections</p> <p>Regional Impact: Cold season precipitation</p> <p>Metrics: Teleconnection with ENSO: Regression of the</p>	<p>Horan et al., 2024 Mehmood et al., 2022, Abid et al. 2020</p>

	monthly grid-box scale precipitation onto the standardized Niño3.4 precipitation index (190–240°E; 5°S to 5°N) as described in Abid et al. (2020)	
WAS	Process: Distribution of snow cover and Snow to Precipitation ratio Regional Impact: Cold season precipitation Metric:	
WAS	Process: Snow to Precipitation ratio Regional Impact: Cold season precipitation Metric:	
WAS	Other poorly defined processes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Indian Ocean Precipitation Dipole (IOPD) • Atmospheric variability 	
SEA	Process: rainfall, temperature, and wind patterns Regional impact: Metrics: a new raking score based on spatial and temporal combinations of: correlation, normalized standard deviation, mean bias, direction of winds on land, as described in Desmet and Ngo-Duc (2021)	Desmet and Ngo-Duc (2021)
SEA	Process: Fundamental characteristics of precipitation, monsoon circulation, ENSO, IOD, teleconnections Regional impact: Metric: a standardised benchmarking framework (Phuong Loan Nguyen et al, 2024)	Phuong Loan Nguyen et al. (2024)
EA, mainly around Japan, Korea, and eastern part of China	Process: East Asian Summer/Winter monsoon Regional impact: Heavy and continuous rainfall in summer, and heavy snowfall in winter. Metric: Various East Asian monsoon indices are proposed, i.e., the northerly wind over the region of 25°N–45°N and 125°E–150°E for winter monsoon (Hu et al. 2000; Kawase et al. 2015), and difference of zonal wind at 850 hPa between	Mizuta et al. (2016)

	5N-15N, 100E-130E and 20N-30N, 110E-140E (Wang et al. 2001; Mizuta et al. 2012).	
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Out of the scope suggestions		
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ESD	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PP, MOS, PP-MOS Hybrid, and weather generators (WGs) - Downscaling statistical parameters directly as opposed to traditional downscaling of climatic states (outcomes) - Hybrid RCM-ESD downscaling - AI in emulation of RCM results - AI as an alternative to traditional statistical methods in downscaling? - Large (n>100) multi-model ensembles and strategies for data structures 	<p>Benestad et al. (2025) doi.org/10.5194/hess-29-45-2025</p> <p>Benestad et al. (2017) doi.org/10.1016/j.cliser.2017.06.013</p>
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SAD	<p>Process: Extreme Monsoon Precipitation (very wet days, extremely wet days, consecutive wet days)</p> <p>Regional Impact: Flood / drought in different homogeneous zones of India hence agricultural crop planning, Potential flood risk and erosion, evaluating prolonged monsoon phases, waterlogging, and crop stress.</p> <p>Metrics:</p> <p>1. Very Wet Days (R95p)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Definition: Annual total precipitation from days when daily precipitation > 95th percentile of daily precipitation on wet days. ● Metric: R95pTOT (mm/year) ● Interpretation: Indicates how much of the total annual rainfall is coming from very wet days, suggesting potential flood risks and erosion. <p>2. Extremely Wet Days (R99p)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Definition: Annual total precipitation from days when daily precipitation > 99th percentile of daily precipitation on wet days. 	
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metric: R99pTOT (mm/year) • Interpretation: Reflects the contribution of extremely intense rainfall events, useful for assessing high-impact weather events. <p>3. Consecutive Wet Days (CWD)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Definition: Maximum number of consecutive days with ≥ 1 mm of precipitation. • Metric: CWD (days) • Interpretation: Indicates persistence of wet spells, which is relevant for evaluating prolonged monsoon phases, waterlogging, and crop stress. <p>4. Additional Metrics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • R10mm: Number of days with precipitation ≥ 10 mm (moderate rain days). • R20mm: Number of days with precipitation ≥ 20 mm (heavy rain days). • Rx1day: Maximum 1-day precipitation amount. • Rx5day: Maximum consecutive 5-day precipitation amount. 	
SAD	<p>Process: Heat wave and Cold wave episodes (Hot Days, warm nights, cold days and cold nights)</p> <p>Regional Impact:</p> <p>Hot Days-Crop sterility, irrigation stress, heat-related illness</p> <p>Warm Nights-Reduced crop recovery, disturbed sleep, urban discomfort</p> <p>Cold Days-Germination delays, respiratory illness, reduced pest pressure</p> <p>Cold Nights-Frost damage, health risk in rural and tribal population</p> <p>Metrics:</p>	

	<p>Hot Days (TX90p)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Definition: Percentage of days when daily maximum temperature (Tmax) > 90th percentile of the reference period (usually 1961–1990 or 1981–2010). <p>Warm Nights (TN90p)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Definition: Percentage of days when daily minimum temperature (Tmin) > 90th percentile. <p>Cold Days (TX10p)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Definition: Percentage of days when daily maximum temperature (Tmax) < 10th percentile <p>Cold Nights (TN10p)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TN10p is the percentage of days in a year when the daily minimum temperature (TN) falls below the 10th percentile of a reference period. 	
SAD	<p>Process: El-Nino and La-Nina events</p> <p>Regional Impact: El Niño and La Niña are the warm and cool phases of the El Niño–Southern Oscillation (ENSO), a recurring climate pattern involving changes in the temperature of waters in the central and eastern tropical Pacific Ocean. These phases strongly influence global weather and climate patterns. For countries like India, El Niño often leads to monsoon failure, affecting rice, pulses, and other crops. La Niña typically brings above-average rainfall, improving crop prospects but increasing the risk of flooding</p> <p>Metrics: Oceanic Nino Index(ONI), Niño SST Indices (Nino 1+2, Nino3, Nino-3.4 and Nino4), Southern Oscillation Index (SOI), Multivariate ENSO Index (MEI)</p> <p>Evaluation Metrics: (Correlation Coefficient (R), the RMSE-observations standard deviation ratio (RSR), Mean absolute error (MAE), Percentage Bias (PB), traditional Quantile Mapping (QM), Quantile Delta Mapping (QDM) and Leave-One-Out-Cross-Validation Framework (LOOCVF) etc</p>	
SAD	<p>Process: Meteorological and Agricultural Drought</p>	

<p>Regional Impact: In South Asia, meteorological and agricultural droughts have widespread impacts. In India, particularly in states like West Bengal and Bihar, weak monsoons and delayed sowing lead to significant yield losses in rice and pulses. In Pakistan, droughts cause reduced water availability, affecting wheat and cotton crops. Bangladesh experiences lower rice yields and water stress during dry spells, while Nepal faces similar challenges with reduced crop productivity. Sri Lanka, especially in its dry zone, suffers from irrigation shortages and lower rice and maize production during drought conditions. The region's dependence on the monsoon makes it highly vulnerable to droughts, leading to food insecurity and economic losses.</p> <p>Metrics:</p> <p>1. Meteorological Drought Metrics</p> <p>i) Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measures precipitation deficits over various time scales (e.g., 1-month, 3-month, etc.). • Values < -1 indicate drought conditions. <p>ii) Palmer Drought Severity Index (PDSI)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tracks soil moisture based on temperature and precipitation. • Negative values indicate drought severity. <p>iii) Rainfall Anomaly</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compares current precipitation to the long-term average. • A negative anomaly indicates a rainfall deficit. <p>iv) Percent of Normal Precipitation (PNP)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measures current rainfall as a percentage of the expected (normal) rainfall for a specific period. • Values below 70% indicate drought. 	
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	<p>2. Agricultural Drought Metrics</p> <p>i) Soil Moisture Anomalies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compares current soil moisture levels with historical averages. • Low values indicate insufficient moisture for crops. <p>ii) Vegetation Health Index (VHI)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Combines vegetation indices (NDVI) and temperature anomalies to assess crop stress. • Low VHI values suggest crop failure or stress. <p>iii) Crop Water Stress Index (CWSI)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measures water stress in crops based on the difference between actual and potential evapotranspiration. • Higher values indicate greater crop stress. <p>iv) Famine Early Warning Systems Network (FEWS NET)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provides monitoring of food insecurity and drought risks through data on rainfall, crop conditions, and soil moisture. 	
ESD	<p>Process: Perfect Prognostic (PP) and Model Output Statistics (MOS) based Empirical Statistical Downscaling (ESD)</p> <p>Regional Impact: Perfect Prognostic (PP) and Model Output Statistics (MOS) based Empirical Statistical Downscaling (ESD) improve regional climate forecasts. In South Asia, these methods help optimize crop planting and irrigation schedules, reducing risks from droughts and floods in regions like West Bengal and Punjab. They also assist in water management in areas like Rajasthan and Andhra Pradesh, guide hydropower generation in Himachal Pradesh, and enhance disaster preparedness in Nepal and Sri Lanka. Overall, these forecasts improve climate adaptation and planning across agriculture, water, and energy sectors in the region.</p>	<p>Journal: Theoretical and Applied Climatology. DOI : 10.1007/s00704-025-05403-4. Title : Identification of homogeneous rainfall zones through machine learning-based clustering algorithm for estimation of rainfall change over the Indo-Gangetic plains of India.</p>

	<p>Metrics:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Correlation Coefficient <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Measures the strength and direction of the relationship between the large-scale model output and observed regional data. ○ High correlation indicates better predictive accuracy. 2. Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Measures the differences between forecasted and observed values. ○ Lower RMSE values indicate better model performance. 3. Mean Absolute Error (MAE) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Evaluates the average magnitude of errors between forecasted and observed data. ○ Lower MAE indicates higher accuracy. 4. Skill Score (SS) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Quantifies the forecast skill compared to a reference forecast (e.g., climatology). ○ A positive skill score indicates better performance than a baseline model. 5. Standard Deviation (SD) of Errors <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Measures the variability in errors across different forecast instances. ○ Lower SD implies more consistent model predictions. 6. Percent of Correctly Predicted Events <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Assesses the accuracy of specific weather or climate events (e.g., precipitation thresholds, drought events). ○ Higher values indicate effective event prediction. 	
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	<p>7. Anomaly Correlation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Measures the correlation between anomalies (deviations from mean) of forecasted and observed data. ○ High correlation suggests good forecasting of patterns. <p>8. Bias</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Identifies systematic errors in the model's overestimation or underestimation. ○ Minimizing bias improves forecast reliability. <p>9. Cross-validation Metrics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Involves dividing the data into training and validation sets to assess model performance. ○ Cross-validated RMSE or MAE can indicate robustness and generalizability. <p>These metrics assess the performance of the PP and MOS methods in downscaling global model outputs to regional climate predictions, ensuring more accurate and reliable forecasts for local adaptation strategies.</p>	
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4. Document history

Date	Comment
2025-05-14	Initial version